

Exercise 2: Reproduce experimental results from a paper

Group 08-A: User-controllable Recommendation Against Filter Bubbles

Experiment Design for Data Science – WS 2023/24

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This report documents a reproduction study of Wang et al.'s paper on "User-controllable Recommendation Against Filter Bubbles" [7]. The study aims to replicate the experimental results and assess the reproducibility of the findings. The results of the paper are validated by re-training the recommender models and re-running the inference procedures with five different random seeds. While most scores are successfully confirmed, minor discrepancies are observed for the Neural Factorization Machine (NFM) model under fine-grained user-feature controls. Statistical testing is omitted due to equal results across random seeds. Despite challenges regarding the setup of the provided source code and the lack of documentation of some software versions and dataset metadata, the overall perception of the paper's reproducibility is positive.

CCS Concepts: • **Information systems** → **Information retrieval**; *Retrieval tasks and goals*; Recommender systems.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: User-controllable Recommender Systems, Counterfactual Inference, Filter Bubbles, Causal Recommendation, Reproducibility, Experiment Design

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1 INTRODUCTION

In their paper "User-controllable Recommendation Against Filter Bubbles" [7] Wang et al. propose a novel recommender prototype called *User-Controllable Recommender System* (UCRS) that gives users control over the mitigation of filter bubbles. The prototype has three objectives: 1) alerting users if they are stuck in filter bubbles, 2) offering them so-called control commands with which they can influence their recommendations, and 3) responding to the control commands so that filter bubbles are mitigated while the accuracy of the recommendations remains high. The framework that revises the recommendations based on user controls is referred to as User-Controllable Inference (UCI).

The paper distinguishes between two categories of control commands. User-feature controls allow the users to receive recommendations that are not typically proposed to their user group, an example of that would be an elderly user expressing the wish to see recommendations for young persons. Item-feature controls are specific to the characteristics of the content that is recommended. With them, users can request more or less content of a certain category. The control

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53 commands have two levels of granularity: Fine-grained user controls can increase the frequency of recommendations
54 related to specific user or item features. If users do not wish to specify any categories that they want to see more often,
55 they can choose to explicitly opt out of certain bubbles (e.g. related to their age) with coarse-grained control commands.
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57 A series of experiments is conducted to evaluate the performance of the UCI and to determine how users can control
58 the recommendations by some coefficients named α and β . Furthermore, the influence of counterfactual inference (as
59 utilized with the control commands) on the recommendations is assessed. The experiments are based on three datasets:
60 DIGIX-Video [3] for evaluating user-feature controls, and ML-1M [1] as well as Amazon-Book [6] for evaluating
61 item-feature controls. The performance of UCI is compared to five baseline algorithms, that are thoroughly described in
62 the original paper. As UCI and the baselines are model-agnostic, they are compared on two recommender models: a
63 Factorization Machine (FM) and a Neural Factorization Machine (NFM) [5].
64

65 In an attempt to replicate the experiment results presented in the paper, we conduct a rigorous investigation to
66 assess the reproducibility of the study’s findings. Our effort involves reviewing the source code provided on GitHub
67 [4] and re-running the experiments multiple times with different random seeds to validate the scores stated in the
68 paper. The chapter [Strategies](#) describes our strategy for reproducing the paper. In the [Difficulties](#) chapter the difficulties
69 regarding reproducibility are documented. Our insights and experiment results are found in the [Key findings](#) chapter.
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72 73 74 75 2 STRATEGIES

76 Our strategy for reproducing and validating the results of the paper is twofold: first, the code from the GitHub repository
77 [4] is re-run on our hardware. We noticed that the scores in the paper lack confidence intervals due to being only
78 evaluated on a single random seed, therefore we re-run the inference code with different random seeds as an additional,
79 second step.
80

81 Reproducing the paper on consumer-grade personal computers imposes the challenge of long running times of the
82 code for training the models and performing inference. To combat this challenge, we use Google Colab to split the
83 training among multiple group members who own hardware with NVIDIA graphic cards. The code hosted on Google
84 Colab is run locally by connecting a local runtime, and the intermediate states of the PyTorch tensors are saved to a
85 common Google Drive directory so that the training can be continued by other group members.
86

87 While reproducing the paper, we encountered challenges with running the code from GitHub that required the code
88 to be slightly modified. To ensure that our changes do not lead to contradictory results to the findings of the paper, we
89 carefully reviewed their impact and documented each change in the [Difficulties](#) chapter.
90

91 Before running inference, the FM and NFM models are re-trained with a random seed of 1 and the parameters
92 mentioned in the *best_models* folder of the GitHub repository. Due to infeasibly long running times, the validation of
93 the parameters by grid-searching the values mentioned in the paper is omitted. For the same reason, the MLP models
94 used for target category predictions for enhancing coarse-grained item-feature controls are not re-trained, instead, the
95 pre-trained models from the GitHub repository are used.
96

97 To validate the results of the paper, the code for inference and re-ranking is run with 5 different random seeds for all
98 models and their corresponding datasets. In case the obtained results vary across the random seeds, standard deviations
99 and confidence intervals are provided for the mean of the scores. The baselines are assumed to be valid and are not
100 re-calculated.
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3 DIFFICULTIES

The authors of the paper took a comprehensive series of measures to ensure the reproducibility of their experiments. The code, the datasets, and a README file containing instructions are provided in the GitHub repository, which is referenced in the paper. The comparison metrics and baselines are discussed in the paper, the experiment setup is well-described and complete. Nevertheless, there are some difficulties regarding reproducibility:

- There is a table in the paper containing statistics on the three datasets, however, metadata such as timestamps, authors, and size is not provided. The paper contains links to the datasets, but no timestamps when they were accessed or who the creators of the datasets are.
- The README file in the GitHub repository provides information on the Python environment and on the versions of the used packages, however it misses essential packages which were required to execute the code without import errors, namely: scipy, seaborn, matplotlib, pandas, openpyxl. There is no information on the operating system and the hardware on which the experiments were run.
- Additional configuration and slight modifications to the code were necessary for us to run the experiments.
- At some places in the code, the random seed does not seem to be set. Corresponding variables are initialized but never used.
- Some of the scores obtained from our experiments differ from the scores in the paper. The differences are small, unfortunately, however, testing for statistical significance is not possible as we obtain the same scores for all 5 seeds.
- The grid-searched values of the epochs and dropout hyper-parameters of the NFM/FM models are missing.

Table 1 provides an overview of the discussed possible problems and whether they occur in the paper.

Difficulty	Occurrence
Code not provided	no
Code partially not provided	no
Faulty code provided	no
Information about software versions missing	partially
Specific hardware and software setup necessary	yes
Data not provided	no
Data partially not provided	no
Metadata not provided	partially
Comparison metrics or baselines not discussed	no
Experimental setup not described	no
Experimental workflow incomplete	no
Inconsistencies in paper, code and data	no
Results differ significantly	no

Table 1. A series of difficulties that can occur while reproducing papers and whether the original paper is affected by them.

Code changes and setup:

Due to a mismatch in the device (CPU or GPU) between the tensor being indexed and the indices used for the indexing operation in PyTorch, a RuntimeError occurred when we tried to execute the code on our hardware. PyTorch requires that the tensor and the indices used for indexing must reside on the same device. If the tensor is on the CPU, the indices

157 must also be on the CPU; if the tensor is on a GPU, the indices should be on the same GPU. For this reason, we modified
 158 all *evaluate.py* files to move the indices to the GPU where the tensors reside.

159 In some inference scripts (namely the two *FM_NFM_inference.py* scripts, *UCI_reranking.py*, *UCI_fine_user_control.py*,
 160 and *UCI_coarse_user_control.py*), a variable named `random_seed` is initialized with the value 1, but the seed is never
 161 set. In other inference scripts (like *C_UCI_inference.py*), the seed value is set to 1 for PyTorch, Numpy, and Python’s
 162 random library. Additionally, `torch.backends.cudnn.deterministic` is set to true. We modified the scripts that lack
 163 the setting of the seeds to take a parameter `seed`, which uses the five seed values from our experiments. Though results
 164 may not be reproducible between CPU and GPU executions even when using identical seeds, setting seeds and the
 165 `torch.backends.cudnn.deterministic` flag limits the number of sources of nondeterministic behavior. [2]

166 When running the code on the latest version of PyTorch at the time of the experiments (2.1.2), an error occurs in
 167 `MLP.forward()` in *model.py* since the implementation of `torch.nn.modules` has changed compared to the PyTorch
 168 version used in the paper (1.4.0). Downgrading PyTorch to the oldest available version (1.11.2) resolves the issue.

172 4 KEY FINDINGS

173 Our experiments validate the scores presented in Table 2 and Table 3 of the original paper (see Table 2 and Table 3).
 174 The scores of the NFM-F-UCI models with counterfactual inference differ slightly from the results of Wang et al. (see
 175 Table 4 and Table 5). In Table 4, the MCD score of the NFM-Reranking algorithm is off by 0.001. The Coverage score
 176 of the NFM-F-UCI is off by 0.005 in Table 5. While we are unable to clearly state the reason for the differences, we
 177 hypothesize that it might be related to slight differences in the weights of the NFM model, resulting from the use of
 178 different library versions or calculation inaccuracies due to different operating systems. It is unlikely that the scores
 179 were changed intentionally in the original paper, as the deviations are not large enough to impact the conclusions.

180 Whether the differences are statistically significant is impossible to determine, as the scores obtained from our
 181 experiments are equal across all 5 different random seeds used for inference. This is a general observation of the
 182 experiments: the results of the inference are always equal, regardless of the random seed. For this reason, we are unable
 183 to provide confidence intervals for our scores. This result leads to the conclusion that the impact of randomness is
 184 negligible for inference. Therefore stating only single scores without confidence intervals is not a flaw of Wang et al.’s
 185 paper, as they most likely also obtained the same results regardless of the seed.

Method	Recall	NDCG	Iso-Index	Coverage
FM	0.0758	0.0584	0.1082	9.5191
FM-UCI	0.0767	0.0592	0.0777	9.8802
NFM	0.0774	0.0585	0.1144	10.2670
NFM-UCI	0.0767	0.0596	0.0760	9.9000

186 Table 2. Performance comparison between UCI and the FM/NFM baselines under the coarse-grained user-feature controls. The table
 187 corresponds to Table 2 in the original paper, all scores could be reproduced and validated.

201 5 CONCLUSION

202 In an effort to reproduce the results of Wang et al.’s paper titled “User-controllable Recommendation Against Filter
 203 Bubbles” we conducted an investigation that re-runs the experiments to confirm the results. As a further validation
 204 measure, we ran the inference with five different seeds to mitigate the effect of randomness involved in the process.
 205 During the procedure, we documented the difficulties we encountered regarding reproducibility.

Model	FM					NFM				
	Recall	NDCG	Iso-Index	DIS-EUC	Coverage	Recall	NDCG	Iso-Index	DIS-EUC	Coverage
FM/NFM	0.0861	0.065	0.1161	0.0568	8.6781	0.0849	0.0630	0.1046	0.0436	9.5126
UCI	0.0870	0.0661	0.0979	0.0516	9.0304	0.0844	0.0635	0.0844	0.0354	9.6439

Table 3. Performance comparison between UCI and the FM/NFM baselines under the fine-grained user-feature controls. The table corresponds to Table 3 in the original paper, all scores could be reproduced and validated.

Model	ML-1M						Amazon-Book					
	Recall	NDCG	W-NDCG	MCD	TCD	Coverage	Recall	NDCG	W-NDCG	MCD	TCD	Coverage
FM-Reranking	0.0761	0.0637	0.0603	0.1000	0.3099	8.9409	0.0178	0.0142	0.0142	0.0026	0.5348	3.0196
FM-C-UCI	0.0770	0.0665	0.0630	0.2466	0.3334	9.1206	0.0173	0.0141	0.0146	0.0213	0.6310	2.0768
FM-F-UCI (UB)	0.2095	0.1704	0.1792	0.3544	1.0000	8.0712	0.0334	0.0283	0.0337	0.0023	1.0000	1.0002
NFM-Reranking	0.0752	0.0672	0.0631	0.0297 <i>(0.0296)</i>	0.3163	9.0468	0.0180	0.0144	0.0144	0.0025	0.5421	3.0184
NFM-C-UCI	0.0778	0.0687	0.0647	0.2753	0.3119	9.0744	0.0181	0.0148	0.0154	0.0049	0.6779	1.4190
NFM-F-UCI (UB)	0.2114 <i>(0.2125)</i>	0.1703 <i>(0.1729)</i>	0.1791 <i>(0.1820)</i>	0.3456 <i>(0.3319)</i>	1.0000	8.0799 <i>(8.2299)</i>	0.0338	0.0276	0.0327	0.0023	1.0000	1.0002

Table 4. Results of item-feature controls on ML-1M and Amazon-Book. The table corresponds to Table 4 in the original paper, some of our scores (bold) of NFM-F-UCI on the ML-1M dataset differ from the ones in the paper (italics).

Method	Variants	Recall	NDCG	W-NDCG	MCD	Coverage
FM-F-UCI	w/o CI	0.2094	0.1689	0.1777	0.3587	7.9519
FM-F-UCI	w/ CI	0.2095	0.1704	0.1792	0.3544	8.0712
NFM-F-UCI	w/o CI	0.2094	0.1687	0.1775	0.3525	8.0160 <i>(8.0155)</i>
NFM-F-UCI	w/ CI	0.2114 <i>(0.2125)</i>	0.1703 <i>(0.1729)</i>	0.1791 <i>(0.1820)</i>	0.3456 <i>(0.3319)</i>	8.0799 <i>(8.2299)</i>

Table 5. Performance comparison with (w/) and without (w/o) counterfactual inference (CI). The table corresponds to Table 5 in the original paper, some of our scores (bold) of NFM-F-UCI differ from the ones in the paper (italics).

Our experiments confirmed most of the scores stated in the original paper. Deviations occurred with the Neural Factorization Machine in combination with the fine-grained User-Controllable Interface. While we were not able to perform statistical testing due to equal results across all random seeds, the differences between Wang et al.'s and our results are small enough to validate the findings and conclusions of the paper.

While there is room for improvement, the overall reproducibility of the paper was rated positively. The issues comprise of lacking information on operating system versions and hardware, as well as missing metadata of the utilized datasets. The source code that is provided on GitHub required some modifications involving the need for configuration for NVIDIA Cuda GPUs. It is worth pointing out that consumer-grade personal computer hardware might not be sufficient for reproducing all parts of the paper, as the complexity of training the FM/NFM models and grid-searching for the most suitable hyperparameters could lead to infeasibly long running times.

To sum up, our experiments aiming to reproduce Wang et al.'s study validated most scores, with minor deviations. Even though statistical testing was hindered by consistent results across random seeds, our results were similar enough to confirm the conclusions of the paper. Despite the lack of some details on the experiment environment and the required changes to the source code before execution, the overall reproducibility of the paper was perceived positively.

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